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Case Report

Possible Neonatal Post-COVID-19 Coagulopathy Presenting with Convulsions: A Case Report

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Abstract

Background and Aim: COVID-19 during pregnancy may lead to neonatal complications. While neonatal infections are usually mild, post-infectious issues such as coagulopathy and neurological symptoms, including convulsions, can occur. This case report describes a neonate with convulsions potentially linked to post-COVID-19 coagulopathy following maternal SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Methods: A full-term neonate born via cesarean section to a mother with prior COVID-19 infection during pregnancy was clinically assessed following onset of convulsions on day 4 of life. The evaluation included laboratory tests (COVID-19 RT-PCR, TORCH screening, coagulation profile, blood counts, D-dimer), imaging studies (abdominal ultrasound, echoencephalography, CT scan of the head), and clinical monitoring. Treatment was administered with plasma transfusion, steroids, antibiotics, vitamin K, and supportive oxygen therapy. Differential diagnosis excluded sepsis, perinatal asphyxia, and other common causes of neonatal convulsions.

Results: The neonate was negative for SARS-CoV-2 by RT-PCR but demonstrated elevated D-dimer levels and imaging evidence of intraventricular hemorrhage. Clinical symptoms included partial convulsions and irritability. Coagulation tests showed abnormalities consistent with a hyperimmune-mediated coagulopathy. With appropriate supportive treatment, the baby stabilized and was discharged without further seizures. The findings support the hypothesis of neonatal post-COVID-19 coagulopathy linked to maternal antibody transfer and hyperimmune response.

Conclusion: Post-COVID-19 coagulopathy causing neonatal convulsions is rare but clinically important, particularly with maternal SARS-CoV-2 infection. Early recognition, exclusion of other causes, and further research are essential to improve outcomes and establish diagnostic and treatment protocols.

Keywords: Neonatal, COVID-19, Coagulopathy, Convulsions, SARS-CoV-2, Neonate, Post-infectious complications

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Introduction

On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) officially declared the novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) a global pandemic, recognizing its rapid spread and severe impact on public health worldwide [1], [2], [3], [4]. In Albania, the first nationwide lockdown was introduced on March 10, 2020, with strict measures including restrictions on public transport, curfews, and limitations on social gatherings to mitigate viral transmission [5], [6].

Pregnant women were quickly identified as a particularly vulnerable population, given their altered physiology, immunological adaptations, and increased susceptibility to infections [7], [8]. Concerns also arose regarding the potential for vertical transmission of SARS-CoV-2 to the fetus. Although definitive evidence of transplacental transmission remains controversial, maternal infection has been associated with placental inflammation, neonatal immune activation, and coagulopathic responses [7], [9]. Furthermore, pregnant women with COVID-19 have been shown to be at greater risk of complications such as preterm birth, preeclampsia, hypertensive disorders, and increased rates of cesarean delivery, raising important concerns for both maternal and neonatal outcomes [8], [10].

In neonates, COVID-19 has generally been characterized as a mild viral illness, with symptoms including cough, fever, diarrhea, and respiratory distress, particularly among infants younger than six months [9], [11], [12] (Figure 1). Nevertheless, emerging evidence has highlighted that some affected neonates may develop severe complications. These include post-infectious inflammatory syndromes, coagulation abnormalities, and, in rare cases, neurological involvement such as seizures and convulsions [7], [9], [11]. Such findings emphasize the importance of close monitoring of this vulnerable age group and the need for continued research to fully elucidate the short- and long-term consequences of neonatal SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Figure 1. Clinical features, transmission routes, and diagnostic testing protocols in neonates exposed to maternal COVID-19 infection. Vertical transmission is considered low risk; however, postnatal transmission from family or hospital sources represents a significant concern. Neonatal presentations include respiratory distress, gastrointestinal symptoms (vomiting, diarrhea), fever, lethargy, and shock. Diagnosis involves RT-PCR testing of nasopharyngeal and rectal swabs, supported by hematological and biochemical markers indicative of infection and systemic involvement [12].

Methods

We report a case of a full-term neonate delivered via cesarean section to a mother with a documented history of COVID-19 infection during pregnancy. The neonate developed convulsions on day 4 of life, prompting a comprehensive clinical evaluation.

- Clinical Assessment and Monitoring:

The neonate underwent continuous clinical observation, with vital signs (heart rate, respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, and blood pressure) closely monitored. Neurological status was evaluated using serial physical examinations and seizure activity was documented by bedside nursing staff and physicians.

- Laboratory Investigations:

Diagnostic work-up included:

- Infectious screening: COVID-19 RT-PCR testing on nasopharyngeal swab and a full TORCH panel to exclude other congenital infections.
- Hematological evaluation: Complete blood count, coagulation profile, fibrinogen, and D-dimer levels to identify potential coagulopathies.
- Biochemical tests: Serum electrolytes, calcium, glucose, and liver/renal function tests were performed to rule out metabolic disturbances.

- Imaging Studies:

- Neuroimaging: Echoencephalography and cranial computed tomography (CT) scans were conducted to evaluate structural brain abnormalities, ischemic or hemorrhagic lesions.
- Other imaging: Abdominal ultrasound was performed to assess systemic involvement and exclude possible abdominal pathologies.

- Therapeutic Management:

The neonate received a multimodal treatment approach, including:

- Fresh frozen plasma transfusion to correct coagulopathy.
- Corticosteroid therapy for suspected inflammatory response.
- Empirical broad-spectrum antibiotics pending exclusion of bacterial sepsis.
- Intramuscular vitamin K supplementation.
- Supportive oxygen therapy via nasal cannula to maintain adequate oxygen saturation.

- Differential Diagnosis:

Perinatal asphyxia, neonatal sepsis, hypoglycemia, hypocalcemia, and other common metabolic or infectious causes of neonatal convulsions were systematically excluded based on clinical, laboratory, and imaging findings.

- Ethical Considerations:

The case was managed in accordance with institutional neonatal care protocols, and informed parental consent was obtained for both diagnostic procedures and publication of anonymized clinical data.

Case Report

A male neonate, referred to as *Baby M*, was born on April 19, 2021, at 41 weeks of gestation via cesarean section. At birth, anthropometric parameters were as follows: birth weight 3500 g, length 36 cm, and head circumference 36 cm. The mother had a documented history of COVID-19 infection during pregnancy.

- Perinatal and Postnatal Adaptation

At delivery, the neonate was vigorous, cried immediately, and did not require resuscitation. He was discharged home in good condition.

On the 4th day of life, the infant developed partial convulsions involving the limbs and facial muscles, associated with irritability and episodes of oxygen desaturation. The recorded axillary temperature was 38.5 °C. The neonate was admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), placed in an incubator, and received oxygen therapy as required.

- Laboratory Findings

- COVID-19 RT-PCR (nasopharyngeal swab): Negative
- TORCH screening: Rubella IgG positive; CMV IgG positive
- Coagulation profile: PT, INR, aPTT, and fibrinogen within normal limits
- Complete blood count (CBC):
 - Hemoglobin: 14.5 g/dL
 - Hematocrit: 30.8%
 - White blood cells (WBC): 5000/ μ L (neutrophils 35.5%, lymphocytes 38.8%, monocytes 15.8%, eosinophils 8.9%, basophils 1.0%)
 - Platelets: 244,000/ μ L
- Other laboratory results: D-dimer markedly elevated at 4.94 μ g/mL; blood group A (II), Rh positive

- Imaging and Instrumental Examinations

- Abdominal ultrasound: Normal findings.
- Cranial ultrasound (echoencephalography): Enlargement of the ventricles without displacement of the midline structures (Figure 2) [12].
- CT scan of the head: Intraventricular hemorrhage was observed without evidence of intracerebral parenchymal lesions (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Cranial ultrasound (echoencephalography) showing ventricular enlargement without displacement of midline structures in a neonate with convulsions on day 4 of life.

Figure 3. Cranial computed tomography (CT) demonstrating intraventricular hemorrhage without evidence of parenchymal brain lesions.

- Hospital Course and Treatment

During hospitalization, the neonate was managed with fresh frozen plasma (FFP) transfusion, corticosteroids, empirical broad-spectrum antibiotics, intramuscular vitamin K, multivitamin supplementation, and supportive oxygen therapy.

- Condition at Discharge (May 21, 2021)

At the time of discharge, the infant demonstrated stable clinical progress:

- Weight: 4020 g
- General condition: Afebrile, seizure-free, calm, feeding effectively, and gaining weight appropriately

- Physical examination: Anterior fontanelle 1 × 1 cm, normotensive; chest and abdominal examinations unremarkable; urogenital and musculoskeletal systems within normal limits

- Final Diagnoses at Discharge:

- Convulsive syndrome
- Post-COVID exposure (maternal history of SARS-CoV-2 infection)
- Sepsis/post-sepsis condition
- Anemia

Despite an extensive diagnostic work-up, common causes of neonatal convulsions, including sepsis, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), perinatal asphyxia, and neonatal multisystem inflammatory syndrome, were excluded.

The most plausible explanation for the clinical presentation was a hyperimmune response secondary to transplacental transfer of maternal SARS-CoV-2 antibodies, which likely contributed to neonatal coagulopathy and subsequent neurological manifestations.

Discussion

COVID-19–associated coagulopathy has been widely documented in adults and is characterized by elevated D-dimer levels, thrombocytopenia, and thromboembolic events [13]. The underlying mechanisms are multifactorial, involving endothelial injury, cytokine storm, and a dysregulated balance between coagulation and fibrinolysis [14]. In adult patients, antithrombotic strategies have been systematically studied to mitigate morbidity and mortality, and clinical guidelines now provide evidence-based approaches for prophylaxis and treatment [13], [15].

In contrast, neonatal COVID-19–related coagulopathy remains poorly characterized. While neonatal multisystem inflammatory syndrome (MIS-N) has been increasingly reported, cases presenting primarily with isolated coagulopathy and neurological involvement are rare [11]. The constellation of clinical findings in the present case—including seizures, elevated D-dimer, and intraventricular hemorrhage—suggests the possibility of a novel entity: neonatal post-COVID-19 coagulopathy. Importantly, unlike adults, neonates may not acquire SARS-CoV-2 infection directly but could instead manifest immune-mediated complications secondary to transplacental transfer of maternal antibodies. These antibodies may trigger aberrant inflammatory or prothrombotic responses, predisposing neonates to coagulopathic complications in the absence of direct viral replication [7], [9].

The elevated D-dimer observed in our patient supports the hypothesis of an activated coagulation and fibrinolytic system. Moreover, the presence of intraventricular hemorrhage without systemic sepsis or disseminated intravascular coagulation suggests that COVID-19–related immunothrombosis may extend to fragile neonatal cerebral vasculature. This aligns with adult data indicating that SARS-CoV-2–driven coagulopathy can present with both thrombotic and hemorrhagic complications [13], [14], [15].

Another relevant consideration is the timing of maternal infection. Even though the neonate tested negative for SARS-CoV-2 by RT-PCR, maternal infection during pregnancy may have induced immune dysregulation, placental inflammation, or endothelial dysfunction, thereby contributing to neonatal vulnerability [7], [8]. This highlights the importance of antenatal follow-up and targeted neonatal surveillance in pregnancies complicated by maternal COVID-19 infection.

Overall, this case underscores a potential new clinical entity and emphasizes the need for vigilance when caring for neonates born to mothers with prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. Future research should focus on elucidating the immunopathological mechanisms of neonatal coagulopathy, defining diagnostic criteria, and establishing management strategies tailored to this population.

Limitations

This case report has several limitations. First, SARS-CoV-2–specific IgG and IgM antibody testing was not performed in either the mother or the neonate, which could have provided additional evidence regarding potential transplacental antibody transfer. Second, the absence of a control group limits the generalizability of the findings. Finally, although an extensive evaluation was performed, other differential diagnoses such as perinatal asphyxia and disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) cannot be completely excluded.

Conclusion

Neonatal post-COVID-19 coagulopathy presenting with convulsions is a rare but clinically significant entity that warrants increased awareness among neonatologists, pediatricians, and perinatal care teams. In the setting of maternal SARS-CoV-2 infection during pregnancy, neonates may develop immune-mediated or prothrombotic complications even in the absence of direct viral infection. This case highlights the importance of considering COVID-19–related coagulopathy in the differential diagnosis of neonatal seizures, particularly when laboratory and imaging findings suggest coagulopathy and intracranial involvement. Further research is crucial to better define this condition, including its diagnostic criteria, underlying pathophysiological mechanisms, and long-term neurological outcomes. Establishing standardized management protocols will also be essential to guide clinical decision-making. Until then, early recognition, comprehensive evaluation, and careful exclusion of other common etiologies such as sepsis, perinatal asphyxia, and metabolic disturbances remain critical to optimizing neonatal outcomes.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there are no competing interests and all the authors are willing on common ground to publish this article without any conflict or distraction.

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